

**DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA**

**DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL
TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2021
AMOUNT IN NAIRA**

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	69,822,706,034.83
2	ADAMAWA	90,374,678,991.11
3	AKWA IBOM	242,270,425,498.16
4	ANAMBRA	55,014,662,462.82
5	BAUCHI	98,109,166,991.29
6	BAYELSA	150,605,097,110.98
7	BENUE	126,925,575,994.87
8	BORNO	84,308,354,127.83
9	CROSS-RIVER	161,546,685,429.38
10	DELTA	205,915,439,122.85
11	EBONYI	43,389,313,062.07
12	EDO	78,486,979,110.00
13	EKITI	85,335,401,791.21
14	ENUGU	68,715,561,724.51
15	GOMBE	82,276,659,276.13
16	IMO	149,514,885,822.32
17	JIGAWA	32,601,347,001.93
18	KADUNA	66,749,724,113.62
19	KANO	127,653,802,386.68
20	KATSINA	55,335,703,649.49
21	KEBBI	52,926,999,907.27
22	KOGI	68,954,367,715.00
23	KWARA	63,664,907,065.09
24	LAGOS	533,812,963,589.55
25	NASARAWA	56,252,908,296.71
26	NIGER	79,254,552,193.33
27	OGUN	155,567,441,984.84
28	ONDO	70,958,044,815.45
29	OSUN	133,363,433,267.43
30	OYO	91,980,781,262.03
31	PLATEAU	132,473,215,503.65
32	RIVERS*	213,167,072,263.10
33	SOKOTO	80,805,277,209.77
34	TARABA	99,888,316,767.44
35	YOBE	60,231,117,742.01
36	ZAMFARA	101,358,569,693.88
37	FCT	52,712,383,799.73
Total		4,122,324,522,778.34

Important Notes

1 Domestic Debt Stock for Thirty Five (35) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2021.

2* Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at March 31, 2021